

SURVEILLANCE CARD_CCHF_Surveillance of ticks in areas at risk of introduction and establishment of the vector

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Surveillance of ticks in areas at risk of introduction and establishment of the vector.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of a change of the geographic distribution/spread of <i>Hyalomma spp.</i> ticks to new areas.
3	Target species and group	Ticks collected from animals.
4	Target sector / production type	Not applicable.
5	Geographical area covered	Areas where <i>Hyalomma marginatum</i> is considered to be absent, but which are at risk of introduction and establishment of the vector (climatic conditions, vegetation, neighbouring endemic areas).
6	Age group	All age groups.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Collection of ticks from wildlife or livestock, including horses (1), living near or in a suitable vector habitat.
8	Sampling time period	Vector period (spring to autumn).
9	Sampling matrix	Ticks.
10	Type of disease indicators	None; species differentiation to determine presence of competent vectors for CCHFV.
11	Sampling unit	Ticks collected from animals are identified individually i) using binocular and identification key (2) or ii) molecular techniques.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Convenience sampling of livestock or of wildlife animals found dead, caught or collected for other surveillance components.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	Tick species identification.

14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	The component can contribute to detection of introduction of the ticks in new areas. However, results cannot be used directly for estimation of detection sensitivity or confidence of freedom since this is a biased (non-representative) sample of an unknown population.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-319-63760-0
18	References	1) Uiterwijk, M., Ibáñez-Justicia, A., van de Vossenbergh, B., Jacobs, F., Overgaauw, P., Nijssen, R., ... & Sprong, H. (2021). Imported Hyalomma ticks in the Netherlands 2018–2020. <i>Parasites & Vectors</i> , 14(1), 1-12. 2) Ticks of Europe and North Africa: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-63760-0
19	Additional comments	A call for the general public to look out for and report Hyalomma spp. ticks on horses can be of use